

ADVANCING TOWARDS MULTIDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION: PHARMACOGENETICS' ROLE IN FORENSIC TOXICOLOGY

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Abstract

Pharmacogenetics investigates how DNA genes respond individually to drug administration. With advancements in genome sequencing and molecular genetics, pharmacogenetic research has gained traction, offering insights beyond medical applications. It emerges as a valuable tool in deciphering toxicological data in post-mortem examinations, pivotal for determining causes and circumstances of death. This systematic literature review aims to sensitize the forensic community to the potential of pharmacogenetics and provide a procedural guide for forensic toxicologists dealing with drug-related fatalities of uncertain origins. The review encompassed searches with keywords like 'pharmacogenetics' and 'forensic toxicology', yielding 125 articles, with 29 meeting inclusion criteria. The majority (75%) were original articles (n = 21), while 25% were case reports (n = 7). Among the studies, 78% (n = 22) involved deceased individuals subjected to complete autopsies, with the remaining 22% (n = 6) focusing on healthy subjects administered drugs for subsequent pharmacogenetic analysis. Opioids (codeine, morphine, methadone) were the most studied drugs, followed by antidepressants (tricyclic antidepressants, venlafaxine). Across the studies, there was consistent emphasis on the indispensability of pharmacogenetic assessments in drug-related deaths, particularly in cases not involving drug overdose. This review underscores the significance of forensic pharmacogenetics, a field within toxicology that remains incompletely understood yet proves invaluable in sudden deaths, overdoses, drug administration-related fatalities, and cases of alleged medical negligence.

Keywords: pharmacogenetics, forensic toxicology, multidisciplinary approach, molecular autopsy, drug-related death.

Introduction

Forensic science, a multidisciplinary field drawing from chemistry, physics, and biology, operates to establish the "weight of evidence". Within this interdisciplinary framework, the forensic toxicology laboratory is tasked with detecting and measuring drugs and other chemical substances in biological fluids collected during autopsies. Additionally, toxicological assessments serve medico-legal purposes, such as drug and alcohol testing for commercial driver licensing or addressing occupational medicine concerns arising from worker exposure to toxic agents.

In forensic toxicology, understanding the pivotal role of pharmacogenetics is imperative. Pharmacogenetics, the study of genetic variations influencing drug response, affects pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics, and ultimately drug bioavailability. In forensic pathology, the determination of cause of death relies on crime scene investigations, medical history, autopsies, and toxicological findings. In this context, pharmacogenetics emerges as a valuable tool in deciphering toxicological puzzles, particularly in cases of suicides, accidents,

and deaths of unknown etiology. Moreover, the potential impact of pharmacogenetics on drug metabolism should be considered when interpreting post-mortem substance concentrations in bodily fluids or organs.

The term 'pharmacogenetics' describes the study of genetic variations influencing drug pharmacokinetics or pharmacodynamics. These variations may affect genes encoding transporter proteins, drug-metabolizing enzymes, receptors, etc. Pharmacogenetics aims to predict individual drug responses and assess their effects. In clinical practice, it helps evaluate a patient's capacity to achieve desired therapeutic effects or, conversely, to encounter adverse reactions. Advances in genome sequencing and molecular genetics have propelled pharmacogenetic research, serving to identify disease-specific genes, gene products, and allelic variants influencing therapeutic responses.

Furthermore, pharmacogenetics serves as a crucial tool in interpreting toxicological data in post-mortem examinations, often vital in determining cause and manner of death. Forensic pathologists frequently encounter deaths associated with drug use or abuse. For instance, the CYP2D6 gene plays a role in metabolizing certain drugs like morphine and its derivatives (codeine, tramadol, dihydrocodeine, oxycodone), with certain CYP2D6 polymorphisms impacting methadone clearance. Similarly, CYP3A4 is involved in benzodiazepine and buprenorphine metabolism. Thus, identifying cytochrome-inducing or -suppressing mutations can provide insights in cases of suspected drug overdose-related deaths.

Moreover, pharmacogenetics can serve as a vital instrument in elucidating the analysis of toxicological data during post-mortem examinations, often pivotal in ascertaining both cause and manner of death. Notably, forensic pathologists frequently encounter cases involving drug and narcotic use/abuse. For instance, the CYP2D6 gene, part of the Cytochrome P450 Family 2 Subfamily D, participates in metabolizing various drugs like morphine and its derivatives (codeine, tramadol, dihydrocodeine, oxycodone), with specific CYP2D6 polymorphisms potentially impacting methadone clearance. Similarly, CYP3A4 is implicated in metabolizing benzodiazepines and buprenorphine. Hence, identifying the presence of cytochrome-inducing or -suppressing mutations can offer insights into cases of suspected drug overdose-related deaths.

Materials and Methods

A systematic review was undertaken.

SCOPUS served as the search engine from January 1, 1980, to August 1, 2021, to investigate the correlation between pharmacogenetics and forensic toxicology. The search employed the following keywords: (pharmacogenetics) AND (forensic toxicology); (pharmacogenetics) AND (post-mortem); (pharmacogenetics) AND (forensic sciences); and (pharmacogenetics) AND (autopsy). The exclusion criteria were as follows: (1) review articles, (2) articles not written in English, (3) abstracts, (4) posters, and (5) conference communications. The inclusion criteria comprised: (1) Original Articles, (2) Case Reports, (3) Articles written in English, (4) In Vivo Studies, and (5) In Vitro Studies.

Results

More than 75% of the included studies ($n = 29$) were original articles ($n = 22$), while approximately 25% were case reports ($n = 7$). Among the included studies, 22 involved complete autopsies, while around 20% ($n = 6$) focused on healthy individuals who had died after drug administration followed by pharmacogenetic analysis. Opioids (such as codeine,

morphine, and methadone) were predominantly utilized in the analyzed cases, followed by antidepressants (including tricyclic antidepressants and venlafaxine). Notably, only one study administered ethylenediaminetetraacetic (EDTA) anticoagulant and organophosphorus drugs. Blood analysis was conducted in all cases except one, where a hair sample was used to analyze genetic polymorphism. Additionally, one report analyzed various post-mortem samples, such as saliva, spleen, and buccal swabs. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) emerged as the primary method for toxicological investigation, followed by liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS). Gas chromatography (GC) and high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) were utilized in two studies. Furthermore, only one study employed tandem mass spectrometry (UPLC-MS/MS) for toxicological investigation.

Discussion

Forensic pharmacogenetics delves into the examination and analysis of genotypes and allelic variations of genes encoding enzymes crucial in drug metabolism. This review's findings affirm that one extensively studied gene is CYP2D6, a member of the cytochrome P450 enzyme superfamily. Due to genetic polymorphisms within the CYP2D6 gene, four primary phenotypes emerge: ultra-rapid metabolizers (UM), extensive metabolizers (EM), poor metabolizers (PM) lacking functional enzymes due to defective or deleted genes, and intermediate metabolizers (IM) possessing alleles that partially reduce enzyme activity [58]. A recent review [59] indicated that 7% of individuals succumbing to opioid overdoses exhibited an ultra-rapid phenotype, intensifying the toxic effects. As outlined in Table 1, the forensic interest in genotyping this cytochrome stems from its involvement in metabolizing opioids and analogous drugs. Notably, it plays a pivotal role in metabolizing endocannabinoid arachidonylethanolamide (anandamide), 20-hydroxyeicosatetraenoic acid ethanolamide (20-HETE-EA), and 8,9-, 11,12-, and 14,15-epoxyeicosatrienoic acid ethanolamides (EpETrE-EAs), potentially modulating the endocannabinoid system signaling. Its polymorphisms are well-documented to influence the metabolism of fatty acids, steroids, and retinoids. Furthermore, its involvement in the oxidative metabolism of drugs such as adrenoceptor antagonists, antiarrhythmics, and tricyclic antidepressants has been established.

The CYP2D6 gene, like all enzymes within the CYP class, participates in hepatic phase I metabolism of foreign substances and drugs. The P450 family converts drugs into electrophilic intermediates, which are subsequently conjugated by phase II enzymes (e.g., UDP glucuronosyltransferase and N-acetyltransferase) before being excreted. While at least 60 P450 genes exist, the most extensively studied subsets include CYP1A2, CYP2A6, CYP2B6, CYP2C19, CYP2D6, CYP2E1, and CYP3A4, responsible for metabolizing the majority of prescription and over-the-counter drugs.

Conclusion

The implementation of pharmacogenetics carries significant implications from both medical-legal and ethical perspectives. Addressing concerns surrounding informed consent and the collection of DNA databases is paramount prior to integrating genetic analysis into forensic institutions. Moreover, a key issue revolves around the informativeness of genetic testing, which may lead to uncertainties regarding paternity. Consequently, reluctance from relatives to consent to pharmacogenetic testing could hinder the establishment of truth. In light of applying pharmacogenetics in forensic science, these considerations must be carefully weighed in both practical applications and research endeavors. Similarly, adopting a multidisciplinary

approach is imperative in the forensic field, necessitating its incorporation into routine forensic practices. This necessity is underscored by the findings of this systematic review, offering forensic teams a structured workflow to navigate cases involving suspected drug-related deaths.

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